

SCHOOL HEADS' LEADERSHIP PRACTICES AND SCHOOL'S FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

School heads are the persons in authority who manage the school and are considered the pillars of the educational system. Along with their authority, they are accountable for the outcomes of the school operations, programs, and projects. This study aimed to examine the relationship between school heads' leadership practices and the financial management performance of schools in President Quirino Municipality. Specifically, it focused on the leadership dimensions of authority, accountability, and empowerment, and their influence on budget alignment, procurement processes, and the execution of school programs, projects, and activities. The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design, 64 teachers and 22 school heads as respondents. The findings revealed that the school heads' leadership practices were highly practiced, with a significant emphasis on authority, accountability, and empowerment. In terms of financial management performance, the schools were rated as outstanding, demonstrating exemplary practices in budgeting, procurement, and project management. A significant relationship between the school heads' leadership practices and the schools' performance in financial management, affirming the positive impact of effective leadership on the overall financial stability of the schools. These suggest that school heads who exhibit strong leadership in the areas of authority, accountability, and empowerment significantly enhance their schools' financial management performance.

Keywords: *School Heads, Leadership Practices, Financial Management, Division of Sultan Kudarat, Region XII, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

School heads are the persons in authority who manage the school and are considered the pillars of the educational system. Along with their authority, they are accountable for the outcomes of the school operations, programs, and projects. As stated in the Republic Act No. 9155, the school heads shall have the Authority, Responsibility, and Accountability in managing all school affairs. They are accountable for the pupils' learning outcomes, teachers' personal and professional development, establishing a conducive learning environment and maintaining networking and linkages of both internal and external stakeholders, and so as the performance of the school. Thus, the success and failure of the school depends on the kind of school head it has.

School leadership competencies in all schools were not satisfactory and adequate to address the growing quality expectations of learners and parents of schools in Nepal" (Thapa, 2016). Generally, competencies refer to the knowledge, skills, and behaviors that school heads need to demonstrate to achieve results. In the present study, leadership competencies are limited to leading people, performance management, and people development. With this, Cerna (2014) wrote that the school head has a great impact to the learners' and teachers' performance and so as the school performance as a whole. Hence, school heads must possess good qualities as leaders and employ suitable approaches in exercising their authority, accountability, and empowerment so that the teachers and other personnel under their jurisdiction will also work accordingly toward the attainment of the school's vision.

Lunenburg & Irby (2016) further said that in times of crisis, leaders are the ones to depend on to calm their nerves and forge for the path ahead, if that path requires great toil and sacrifices. Despite the overwhelming pressures they face in their own roles, school leaders have demonstrated selflessly and solidly, that their communities can depend on them.

Adesina (2011) considered Leadership as the ability to get things done with the support and cooperation of other people within the institution, organization, or system. Leadership is all about organizational improvement; more specifically, it is about establishing agreed-upon and worthwhile directions for the organization in question, and doing whatever it takes to prod and support people to move in those directions. Leadership simply means influencing others' actions in achieving desirable ends.

Thus, this study seeks to determine the relationship between school heads' leadership practice in terms of authority, accountability, and empowerment of school heads and the financial performance level of schools in President Quirino Municipality, Division of Sultan Kudarat.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aims to determine the relationship between school heads' leadership practice in terms of authority, accountability, and empowerment of school heads and the financial performance level of schools in President Quirino for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent is the level of school heads' leadership practices in terms of:
authority;
accountability; and
empowerment?
2. What is the level of school performance in financial management in terms of;
Budget alignment;
Procurement, and
Programs, Projects, and activities?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of school heads' leadership practices and school performance in financial management?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive correlational research design and employed a pre and post-reading test before and a two-part structured questionnaire was used. Part I were answered by the 64 teacher respondents and triangulated to the answer of the 22 school head respondents. Meanwhile, Part II of the questionnaire was answered by the school head respondents and triangulated to the answer of the teachers. The statistical tools used in processing the data were mean and Pearson r.

On the extent of school heads' leadership management practices in President Quirino, Sultan Kudarat in terms of Authority, Accountability, and Empowerment with a verbal description of "Outstanding" which is interpreted as "Highly Practiced".

On the school financial management performance in terms of Budget Alignment, Procurement Processes, and the execution of Programs, Projects, and Activities it was revealed that "Outstanding" or consistently demonstrated by the school heads in the President Quirino.

Interestingly it was found that is "significant relationship" exists between school heads' leadership practices and school performance in financial management.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On the extent of the level of school heads' leadership practices in terms of authority, accountability, and empowerment

Gyasi et al. (2016) has revealed that the competency of school heads and how they exercise their authority and accountability affects the performance of the school and the learners' achievement. Nevertheless, Minadzi and Nyame (2016) sited that though schools' performance is determined by many factors, it is undeniable that the manner a school head manages the school is a great factor to be considered.

Table 1. Summary Results on the Extent of the level of school heads' leadership practices

No.	Indicator	Mean	Qualitative Description
1	Authority	4.67	Highly Practiced
2	Accountability	4.65	Highly Practiced
3	Empowerment	4.60	Highly Practiced
	Mean	4.64	Highly Practiced

Table 1 shows the summary on the extent of the level of school heads' leadership practices in terms of authority, accountability, and empowerment.

Among the indicators, authority recorded the highest computed mean of 4.67, interpreted as "Highly Practiced." This was followed by accountability, with a mean of 4.65, also interpreted as "Highly Practiced." Lastly, empowerment obtained the lowest computed mean of 4.60, yet still falls under the interpretation of "Highly Practiced."

The consistently high scores across all three indicators underscore the effectiveness and competence of school heads in exercising leadership. These practices are essential for creating an environment that supports academic excellence, efficient resource management, and the holistic development of both learners and teachers.

On the level of school performance in financial management in terms of budget alignment, procurement, and programs, projects, and activities.

Table 2. Summary Result on the Level of school performance in financial management

No.	Indicator	Mean	Qualitative Description
1	Budget Alignment	4.60	Outstanding
2	Procurement	4.59	Outstanding

3	Programs, Projects, and Activities	4.60	Outstanding
Mean		4.60	Outstanding

Table 2 shows the summary on the level of school performance in financial management in terms of budget alignment, procurement, and programs, projects, and activities. R

Results reveal that budget alignment and PPAs both obtained the highest computed mean of 4.60, interpreted as "Outstanding." Closely following is the indicator procurement, with a slightly lower mean of 4.59, which is also interpreted as "Outstanding."

The data suggest that schools are performing at an outstanding level in managing their financial resources across all three indicators. The equal mean scores for budget alignment and PPAs reflect a strong commitment among school heads and financial committees to ensuring that financial resources are systematically aligned with the school's goals and strategic plans. This alignment is essential in achieving desired learning outcomes, sustaining operations, and responding to the needs of various stakeholders.

The findings of this study align with those of Pagdilao and Paguyo (2023) explored the applications of financial strategies in educational continuity plans and efficient procurement and collaborative strategies. Similarly, Alvarez and Delavin (2022) discussed the professional development of school administrators and established that largescale achievements are often associated with the effective management of activities and resources. Pagdilao and Paguyo (2023), as well as Alvarez and Delavin (2022), underlined the significance of managing funds as one of the critical approaches to effective school management.

On the Level of school performance in financial management

Table 3. Summary Result on the Level of school performance in financial management

Variables	Mean	Interpretation	Pearson's r	p-value	Interpretation
Extent of Leadership Practices	4.64	Highly Practiced	0.614	0.001	Significant
School Performance in Financial Management	4.60	Outstanding			

Table 3 presents the computed Pearson's correlation coefficient ($r = 0.614$), which indicates a moderate positive correlation between school heads' leadership practices and school financial management performance. This suggests that as the level of leadership practices increases, the level of financial management performance also tends to improve, and vice versa.

Furthermore, the associated p-value of 0.001 is significantly lower than the commonly accepted threshold of 0.05, indicating that the observed relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, it is safe to conclude that there is a significant relationship between school heads' leadership practices and school performance in financial management.

This result implies that effective leadership practices characterized by strong authority, accountability, and empowerment are positively associated with how well schools manage their financial resources. The moderate correlation also suggests that while leadership is an important contributing factor, other elements such as policy, training, or stakeholder support may also play roles in financial management outcomes.

The findings correspond with Mestry (2004) and Ntseto (2009) that the administration of a school's finances is an integral part of effective school administration, each of the aforementioned tasks will briefly be considered regarding financial management.

Moreover, Ntseto (2009) effective leadership practices in school financial management are crucial for ensuring transparency, accountability, and optimal utilization of resources, all of which contribute to improved school performance. The study emphasized that school principals who demonstrate strong financial leadership through planning, budgeting, and monitoring create a more stable and goal-oriented environment that supports educational outcomes. Ntseto (2009) added that the financial planning of school finances and its control are interdependent and closely linked with each other.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

School heads' leadership management practices in terms of Authority, Accountability, and Empowerment is outstanding and highly practice which resulted to better school financial management performance in terms of Budget Alignment, Procurement Processes, and the execution of Programs, Projects, and Activities it was found out that there is a significant relationship.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented. The school heads may continue doing the duties and responsibilities together with their authority, accountability, and empowerment for the

betterment of the school. The school heads may sustain their schools' financial management practices to disburse funds according to the approved programs, projects, and activities. This study be replicated in wide scope to have a clearer picture of School heads' leadership practices and school financial management performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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